

A review on synthesis and applications of nanomaterials

V. U. Rahangdale*, S. D. Charpe¹

Jagat Arts, Commerce and I.H.P. Science College, Goregaon, Dist. Gondia, Maharashtra- 441801 India

¹Department of Physics, J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur Dist. Amravati, Maharashtra-444803,

E-mail address of corresponding author: vijayrahangdale11@gmail.com

Abstract

Nanotechnology has very broad range of potential applications in the field of physics, biology and medicine on nanoscale. Nanomaterials are the group of materials that have at least one dimension in the range of 1 to 100 nm. As these materials possess exceptionally important properties at nanoscale level, it is important to study the different synthesis methods related to nanomaterials to explore them. This review article gives deep inside about the physical methods of synthesis of nanomaterials and their applications, which may be helpful for researchers.

Keywords: History, classification, synthesis methods, applications of nanomaterials.

1 Introduction

From the beginning of 19th century nanotechnology branch is flourishing to a great extent. Today lot of research is going on related to the nanotechnology. Nanotechnology can be stated as the developing application of materials and devices by modifying their dimensions in nanoscale. "Nano" word is derived from the Greek word nanos or Latin word nanus which means "dwarf". Materials are said to be nanomaterials if their size or one of their dimensions is in the range of 1 to 100 nm [1].

Although nanotechnology is new, but research on nanometer scale is done in very early time. Colloidal dispersions and metallic quantum dots have been in the nanometer scale for centuries. Chinese people were using gold nanoparticles as an inorganic dye for applying red color in ceramic porcelains more than thousand years ago [2, 3]. The nanomaterials show different properties compared to the bulk material which depends on their size and shape. So to introduce a new characteristic in a material it must be modified with its shape and size at the nanoscale level. Nanomaterials may be of different shapes like nanorods, nanoparticles, nanosheets which are characterized based on dimensions. Nanomaterials with zero-dimensional are nanoparticles, one dimensional is nanorods or nanotubes and two dimensional are in the form of films and layers type. The nanomaterials are of different types based on their morphology, size, properties and the constituent in it. They are carbon-based nanomaterials, metal nanoparticles, semiconductor nanomaterials, polymeric nanomaterials, lipid-based nanomaterials.

It is not easy to cover all the synthesis methods of nanomaterials and applications, Therefore this review attempts to provide information about the physical methods for the synthesis and applications of nanomaterials by referring important papers from history and the current literature.

2 Synthesis Methods of Nanomaterials

The synthesis of nanoparticles can be done by following methods

- (1) Physical methods
- (2) Chemical methods and
- (3) Biological methods

In this review article only physical methods for the synthesis of nanomaterials have been discussed.

2.1 Synthesis of nanomaterials by Physical route

The physical methods are categorized to “top-down” and “bottom-up” approaches. In “top-down” approach the larger materials are crushed into smaller particles by mechanical milling. The problem with top-down approach is the imperfection of the surface structure and difficulty in getting desired particle size and shape [4, 5].

Fig. 1 Synthesis of nanomaterials via top-down and bottom-up approaches [6]

It is well known that the conventional top-down techniques such as lithography can cause substantial crystallographic damage to the processed patterns and additional defects may be introduced even during the etching steps [7, 8]. Bottom-up approach is often emphasized in nanotechnology literature, though bottom-up is nothing new in materials synthesis. In the “bottom-up” method either liquid or gaseous phase, nanoparticles are condensed in which the larger materials are formed by the chemical combination of the smaller ions.

2.1.1 Top-down approaches

In top-down approaches, bulk materials are divided to produce nanostructured materials. Top-down methods include mechanical milling, etching, and sputtering and laser ablation. In this article mechanical milling process for the synthesis of nanomaterials has been discussed.

Mechanical milling

Mechanical milling is a cost-effective method for producing materials at the nanoscale level from bulk materials. Mechanical milling is an effective method for producing blends of different phases, and it is helpful in the production of nanocomposites. The principle of the ball milling method is shown in Fig. 2

Fig. 2 The principle of the ball milling method [9]

Mechanical milling is used to produce wear-resistant spray coatings, aluminum and copper-based nanoalloys, and many other nanocomposite materials [10]. Ball-milled carbon nanomaterials are considered a novel class of nanomaterial, which provides the opportunity to satisfy environmental remediation, energy storage, and energy conversion demands [11].

2.1.2 Bottom-up approaches

Bottom-up approaches includes chemical vapor deposition, sol-gel method, and soft & hard templating method. Here chemical vapor deposition for the synthesis of nanomaterials has been discussed.

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD)

Chemical vapor deposition is more difficult than physical vapor deposition but it has benefits including the capacity to create pure thin films or nanoparticles, high manufacturing yield, and simplicity in scaling up. Chemical vapor deposition method is generally used in the synthesis of carbon-based nanomaterials. In CVD, a thin film is formed on the substrate surface via the chemical reaction of vapor-phase precursors [12]. A precursor is considered suitable for CVD if it has adequate volatility, high chemical purity, good stability during evaporation, low cost, a non-hazardous nature, and a long shelf-life. Moreover, its decomposition should not result in residual impurities [12]. For instance, in the generation of carbon nanotubes via CVD, a substrate is placed in an oven and heated to high temperatures. Subsequently, a carbon-containing gas is slowly introduced to the system as a precursor. At high temperatures, the decomposition of the gas releases carbon atoms, which recombine to form carbon nanotubes on the substrate [13]. However, the choice of catalyst plays a significant role in the morphology and type of nanomaterial obtained.

3. Applications of Nanomaterials

Nanotechnology and nanomaterials can be applied in all kinds of industrial sectors. They are usually found in these areas:

- A) **Electronics:** Carbon nanotubes are close to replacing silicon as a material for making smaller, faster and more efficient microchips and devices, as well as lighter, more conductive and stronger quantum nanowires. Graphene's properties make it an ideal candidate for the development of flexible touchscreens.
- B) **Energy:** A new semiconductor developed by Kyoto University makes it possible to manufacture solar panels that double the amount of sunlight converted into electricity. Nanotechnology also lowers costs, produces stronger and lighter wind turbines, improves fuel efficiency and, thanks to the thermal insulation of some nanocomponents, can save energy.

C) Biomedicine: The properties of some nanomaterials make them ideal for improving early diagnosis and treatment of neurodegenerative diseases or cancer. They are able to attack cancer cells selectively without harming other healthy cells. Some nanoparticles have also been used to enhance pharmaceutical products such as sunscreen.

4. Conclusion

In recent days the synthesis of nanomaterials are increasing with novel and advanced technology. The nanomaterials with mixed compositions are also synthesizing to apply in different fields. Synthesis methods discussed in this article will produce the nanoparticles of desired size, shape and property which will be used for various applications. Therefore, the present review article will provide an opportunity to make general information about the nanoparticles. Nanotechnology can be used in recycling and removing contamination from the wastewater. Nowadays wide research is going into the fields of electronics and storage devices, sensors and medicine but still there is a scope for the development of research in nanotechnology.

References:

1. Nanostructure and Nanomaterials by Guozhong Cao, Imperial College Press 57 Shelton Street Covent Garden London 2004.
2. J. Ayers, in *Ceramics of the World: From 4000 BC to the Present*, eds. L. Camusso and S. Bortone, Abrams, New York, p. 284, 1992.
3. H. Zhao and Y. Ning, *Gold Bull.* 33, 103 (2000).
4. Thakore Sonal et al., *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C* 44 (2014) 209–215.
5. S. Dutz, R. Hergt, J. Mürbe, R. Müller, M. Zeisberger, W. Andrä, J. Töpfer, M.E. Bellemann, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 308 (2007) 305–312.
6. P. Khanna, A. Kaur and D. Goyal, *J. Microbiol. Methods*, 2019, 163, 105656
7. B. Das, S. Subramaniam, and M.R. Melloch, *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* 8, 1347 (1 993).
8. C. Vieu, E Carcenac, A. Pepin, Y. Chen, M. Mejias, L. Lebib, L. Manin Ferlazzo, L. Couraud, and H. Launois, *Appl. Surf: Sci.* 164, 11 1 (2000).
9. S. Zhuang, E. S. Lee, L. Lei, B. B. Nunna, L. Kuang and W. Zhang, *Int. J. Energy Res.*, 2016, 40, 2136–2149.
10. Prasad Yadav, R. Manohar Yadav and D. Pratap Singh, *Nanosci. Nanotechnol.*, 2012, 2, 22–48.
11. H. Lyu, B. Gao, F. He, C. Ding, J. Tang and J. C. Crittenden, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, 2017, 5, 9568–9585
12. A. C. Jones and M. L. Hitchman, in *Chemical Vapour Deposition*, ed. A. C. Jones and M. L. Hitchman, Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge, 2008, pp. 1–36.
13. K. A. Shah and B. A. Tali, *Mater. Sci. Semicond. Process.*, 2016, 41, 67–82.